

A REVIEW ON TREATMENT METHODS OF DISTILLERY SPENT WASH

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Abstract

Distilleries produce large acidic, recalcitrant and colourful industrial effluents with a high organic content. The chemical molecules known as melanoidin are responsible for the dark hue of distillery wastewater. Disposing of wastewater into the ecosystem is dangerous and has the potential to pollute the environment. It decreases UV radiation from penetration of light in freshwater resources, lowering photosynthesis rate and dissolved oxygen concentrations, while also lowering soil alkalinity and inhibiting germinating seeds on land. As a result, one of the most pressing environmental problems is the management of this produced wastewater. To treat this effluent, a variety of techniques including aerobic, anaerobic, physical and chemical methods have been used.

It has proven to be effective in dealing with organic and inorganic pollutants while producing little or no by-products trash. Over the last decade, a large number of studies have been dedicated to using electrocoagulation to treat a variety of wastewaters, ranging from polluted groundwater to severely polluted petrochemical wastewater. The studies revealed that the technologies concept, possible applications, current obstacles and latest developments as well as cost-effective issues. The majority of recent EC studies have been focused on pollutant-specific assessment without considering reactor design, simulation or industrial programmes.

Keywords: Distillery Spent Wash, Melanoidins, Molasses, Alcohol production.

1. INTRODUCTION.

The world's largest water consumption rates are highly pronounced due to ever-increasing populations, so pure and clean water is one of the most present and future demands that humanity faces. Fresh water surface resources are currently being constantly degraded as a result of the incursion of effluents. Wastewater reuse and recycling has become an absolute necessity for rekindled interest in creating cost-effective, dependable, and environmentally friendly that can reuse the huge amounts of wastewater generated by various sectors. Physical, chemical, and biochemical characteristics are the three major groups of wastewater treatment technologies. Wastewater treatment technologies exist and have been used for a long time, majority of them consume a large amount of energy. Physical approaches rely on the physical removal of contaminants from wastewater without significantly altering the treated wastewater biological or chemical characteristics. Chemical techniques require the large amounts of chemical to react with contaminants and remove them, hence they are externally chemical additive procedures. However, they raise the amount of net dissolved solids in effluent. Biological approaches make use of microbes for the biological degradation of contaminants in wastewater, with the primary goal of reducing organic matter and nutrients in the effluent. Biological processes are classified as aerobic, anaerobic or fermentative, depending on the amount of dissolved oxygen in the effluent.

Molasses wastewater is produced by distilleries, sugar industry and other related industries. Molasses which is generated from sugar mills, it is usually because of its simple availability and low cost, corn is the most common feedstock used in ethanol manufacturing. India is Asia's second-largest ethanol producer, currently 319 distilleries producing 3.25 billion litres of alcohol [1] and [2]. According to the (CPCB) Central Pollution Control Board, distillery industries are one of India's top 17 polluting industries. Researches revealed

that, one litre of ethanol produces ten to fifteen litres of distillery spent wash generated, and a typical distillery produces approximately half million litres of effluent everyday [3-4]. In India, annual effluent production is estimated to be 40 billion gallons for the production of 2.3 billion litres of alcohol.

When these distillery spent wash (DSW) are release into streams, ponds as well as other fresh water, they affect dissolved oxygen in water and cause further problems; if they have been released on land, they affect properties of soil, seedling growth and greenery; and melanoidin colours are hazardous to microbes in water and soil [5]. The DSW brownish colour makes microbial breakdown and biological treatment technologies difficult [6]. Melanoidins have troublesome compounds, thus traditional colour removal processes are ineffective and anaerobic treatment methods result in colour darkening due to re-polymerization of compounds [7]. After traditional treatment, effluent handling is hazardous and has an especially in high risk possibilities due to the growth of non-biodegradable recalcitrant pollutants, which have a high colour and have a massively complicated melanoidin state with anti-oxidant properties, starting to cause poisonous to many microbes that are active in wastewater treatment systems [8]. DSW causes a reduction in pH value of freshwater resources, an increase in organic matter content and an intolerable odour. This review paper illustrates that, the treatment methods of distillery spent wash using conventional methods for the degradation of different parameters.

Table 1: Wastewater Characteristics of Distillery Spent Wash [9]

Parameter	Values
Colour	Dark brown
Odour	Unpleasant burn
pH	4.80
TDS (mg/L)	91700
TSS (mg/L)	26560
TS (mg/L)	118260
BOD (mg/L)	43000
COD (mg/L)	128000
Organic Carbon (%)	3.7
Nitrogen (mg/L)	1460
Phosphorus (mg/L)	326
Potassium (mg/L)	14300
Calcium (mg/L)	6800
Magnesium (mg/L)	4384
Chloride (mg/L)	10650

1.1 Effect of pH, TDS, Colour, BOD, COD

1.1.1 pH

Wastewater pH influence the aquatic organisms within that area and may leads to demise of fishes. pH effects the dissolving and toxicity of chemicals and heavy metals present in the water. The most of aquatic life desires pH range of 6.5-9.0, but some aquatic life active beyond this range. As a pH level fluctuate beyond that desirable range it can cause stress animal systems and reduce hatching and death rates. Desirable pH range keeps high mortality rates, sensitive species greatly affected by pH range fluctuation. Other than this, great pH levels usually increases the dissolvability of chemicals and danger of absorption by aquatic life [10].

1.1.2 Colour

Light is the most essential for the growth of aquatic plants and dark brownish color water will reduce the penetration of light into the deep water. Dark brownish colored water has severe effect on aquatic plants and algal growth. Hence excess colored water could not with stand aquatic plant life which may leads to long term imbalance of the aquatic ecosystem. Higher the algal growth that suspended in a water ecosystem will prevent light penetration and uses the dissolved oxygen that present in the water, triggering the chance of eutrophic condition that can significantly decrease all aquatic life in the water ecosystem [11].

1.1.3 BOD

The amount of DO in water bodies are influenced by biological oxygen demand (BOD). Higher the BOD, faster is the oxygen in the stream depleted. It shows that higher forms of aquatic ecosystems have a limited supply of oxygen. Higher BOD levels can cause same problems as low dissolved oxygen levels in water: aquatic life becomes stressed, suffocates and dies [12].

1.1.4 COD

Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) is a criteria that can be used to assess the impact of wastewater discharged into the environment. Increased COD levels indicates that more oxidizable organic particles in the water, resulting in lower dissolved oxygen levels. Higher aquatic life forms are harmed when levels drop, resulting in the anaerobic conditions [12].

1.1.5 TDS

By raising salinity, total dissolved solids can produce toxicity, altering the ionic content of the water and enhancing the toxicity of particular ions. Higher salinity causes swings in biotic groups, degrade biodiversity and reduces the less-tolerant species and can cause moderate or chronic effects at specific life stages [13].

1.2 Nature of melanoidins

Melanoidins are a naturally occurring complex biopolymer that is produced through a non-enzymatic browning event known as the Maillard Amino-Carbonyl reaction, which occurs between amino and carbonyl groups in organic matter [14-15]. Melanoidins are found mostly in foods, beverages and wastewater discharge from sugar mills, distilleries and fermentation plants. Melanoidins continue to pose a threat to aquatic and surrounding ecosystems due to its structural complexity, dark hue and foul odour. At the moment, the most visible environmental concern posed by melanoidin pollution is eutrophication in accepting natural waters sources, as sunlight penetration decreases, photosynthesis activity decreases and dissolved oxygen concentrations in surface waters fall [16-17]. Pant et al., (2007a) proposed the empirical formula for melanoidins as $C_{17-18}H_{26-27}O_{10}N$ [18]. Cammerer et al., (2002) have depicted the basic structure of melanoidin [19] in Fig.1. Melanoidin has a molecular weight distribution that ranges from 5-40 kDa. It contains acids, polymers and extensively dispersed colloidal particles with negative charges as a result of dissociations of carboxylic acid and phenoilc group [20].

Figure 1. Basic structure of melanoidins by Cammerer et al., (2002) [20].

2 ALCOHOL PRODUCTION PROCESS.

2.1 Process of Alcohol Manufacturing

Figure 2 depicts the several processes in the alcohol process of production, which include feed preparations, fermenting, distilling, and packaging.

Figure 2. A process flow diagram

2.1.1 Feed Preparation

Canes, Beets, Molasses and Fruits will be used as sugar bases rehabilitated to ethanol, also sugar, cellulose and starch are the raw materials essential for ethanol production [21]. Materials like cassava, corn, rice, wheat and barley are used as starch bases and crop residuals, woods and sugar cane bagasse are used as cellulose base [22]. In Brazil cane extracted juice is used as a feedstock for ethanol production [23]. In Indian distilleries sugar molasses are the raw material for ethanol production and also world ethanol production is about 61% from sugar crops [24].

2.1.2 Fermentation

Blackstrap molasses is the utmost used sugar base for ethanol fermentation is having 35–40 weight % of sucrose, glucose and fructose is about 15–20 weight % as invert sugar and other than sugar solids content is about 28–35 weight % . Blackstrap or effluent syrup from sugar mill is collected as a by-product. Cane molasses, beet molasses and cane juice is diluted before use [25–26], *Zymomounas mobilis* cultures are used for ethanol manufacture. *Saccromyces cerevisiae* and *Saccharomyces pombe* bacteria are used in fermentation process. Bacteria or yeast culture is prepared by keeping 0.5 litre molasses for one day incubation period. After one day bacteria culture are grown in 5 litre molasses for another day. For growth of yeast culture range of pH 3.0-3.2 is most encouraging as development of yeast will be quicker. Nutrient supply used is 2000 gm urea, 2000 gm Diammonium Phosphate (DAP) for bacterial culture development. Under control condition of temperature and pH this anaerobic development has conceded while sugar brakes down reduced to ethyl alcohol with carbon dioxide. 25-35 °C of temperature has maintained by use of flat plate heat exchange unit or by use of water spray coolers with fermenter barriers. Each batch of fermentation requires time period range between 24-36 hours and provides 95 % efficiency. Continuous reactor or batch reactors used for Fermentation

process (CPCB 2003). From which effluent is released as waste water from the remaining fermented webbing is termed as distillery spent wash [27].

2.2 Impact of Distillery effluent on Environment

The following are some of the environmental effects of distillery wastewater.

- Discharging wastewater with high TDS levels has a negative impact on aquatic ecosystems, making water unsafe for drinking, reducing crop output if used for irrigation and causing pipe line corrosion.
- Light penetration and plant food production will be effected if water has more suspended particles within it which increases turbidity and cause the clogging of gills of fishes.
- Anaerobic condition occurs due to higher BOD contents which encourage organic matter decomposition which leads to offensive gases like methane, ammonia and hydrogen sulphide gas.
- Falling level of DO in surface water sources effect the aquatic ecosystem as DO reduction cause threatening for fish and other species and may leads to death.
- Lowering the DO range causes unpleasant odours and tastes, as well as lowering the water's tolerability for household usage.
- Distillery wastewater changes the pH of receiving waters, affecting aquatic ecology. Extreme acidity results in the creation of H₂S, which is released into the atmosphere.
- Distillery effluent has dark red brown in color with disagreeable odour.
- Distillery spent wash is a multi-component stream that has been shown to create considerable fouling.

3. TREATMENT TECHNOLOGIES FOR DISTILLERY SPENT WASH.

As a result of the large changes occurring in the vicinity of distillery facilities and ecological crises, there is an immediate need for change and scientific advancement. These industries also have a significant impact on the soil surface and aquatic environment. In order to reduce and cost-effectively dispose of effluent in the current context, a number of ways are developing to treat distillery discharge and, as a result, reduce environmental contamination. At present new and huge numbers of approaches are discovered to decrease pollution problem of distillery spent wash.

3.1 Adsorption

Adsorption is speedy process of passive sequestration and disintegration of adsorbate from liquid or gassy state against solid state. Activated carbon is very familiar adsorbent due to its large surface area and micro-porous arrangements of particles, it has great adsorption capability and great amount of superficial reactivity. Among several physico-chemical treatment methods, activated carbon adsorption is widely utilised for the elimination of colour and specific organic waste. Cane molasses and charcoal as adsorbents for decolorization of distillery spent wash [28-29]. Because of its enormous surface area, micro porous structure, high adsorption capacity, and high degree of surface reactivity, activated carbon is a well-known adsorbent [30]. Activated carbon is widely utilised in the wastewater treatment industry to remove organic contaminants.

3.2 Oxidation process

For the treatment of distillery effluent, oxidation methods such as ozone, hydrogen peroxide, ozone combined with hydrogen peroxide and fenton method to be used. The ozone approach was capable of removing 76 % of colour and combining ozone with a lower concentrations of hydrogen peroxide increased the colour removal efficacy to 89 % [31]. Limitations of ozone method is initial cost is very high of setting up and production of greater amount of ozone, fenton's reagent, single phase treatment by ozone, electrochemical oxidation method is not sufficient for huge scales because of greater reagent cost and not suitable for treating industrial waste water [32]. Hydrogen peroxide and Fenton's reagent are not effective for removing color [31].

3.3 Aerobic treatment

Aerobic method of treating molasses effluent adopted for the color removal from main colorant present called melanoidins and also reduce the content of COD and BOD. In recent years, various microorganisms like as bacteria (pure and mixed culture), cyanobacteria, yeast and fungi have been utilised to treat melanoidins and thereby remove colour from molasses wastewater [33].

3.4 Anaerobic Treatment

Physico–Chemical and Biological methods are adopted on huge scale to treating the distillery effluent (DSW). Biological treatment is more suitable if COD/BOD ratio is higher than 1.5 for treating distillery spent wash. In absence of oxygen biological process take place and energy is taken out from the waste constituents. Anaerobic method has high capability of decomposition and produces lesser sludge, needs less power and is advantageous by producing methane gas and is used for steam production in boiler, this method requires more hydraulic retention time (HRT) and is very sensitive to organic shock loadings because of lower pH spent wash and delayed growth rate of anaerobic microorganisms. Hence it can be said that anaerobic method has poor performance. At present anaerobic method is efficiently adopted to disintegrate distillery effluent and produce biogas [34]. Anaerobic lagoon or digester is the modest and older method used formerly on huge scale. But this technique has numerous drawbacks and disadvantages such as large area is required, smell nuisance, variations of ground water contamination.

3.5 Phytoremediation

Phytoremediation of wastewater is an evolving, less budget method for elimination of toxicants comprising metals from industrial effluent, and it is now in the research stage. The potential of aquatic plants to reduce the levels of harmful metals, BOD, and total organic solids in effluents is exceptional. Used a built wetland made up of four cells to treat distillery wastewater [35]. Waste water was initially pre-treated in the first two cells before being channelled to the third and fourth cells, which contain plants *Typha latifolia* and *Phragmites karka*. This approach removed 85 percent of the biological oxygen demand, 64 percent of the chemical oxygen requirement, 42 percent of total solids and 79 percent of the phosphorus content.

3.6 Activated sludge process

The activated sludge process is the most widely used technique of treating wastewater, and research efforts are focused on improving reactor layout and efficiency. For the time being, an aerobic SBR is able to treat waste water generated by small-scale wineries [36]. A primary settling tank, an intermediary retaining channel, two storage tanks, and an aerobic treatment tank were all part of the treatment plant. Bio composting is an aerobic digesting technology that uses activated bio transmissions. Depending on the availability of organic material and the presence of inorganic materials required for their growth, several types of microorganisms breakdown carbonaceous components. Composting is primarily used to convert complicated wet constituents into a simple useable form, thereby stabilising organic molecules and killing pathogenic bacteria through proper dehydration of the wet substances. In aerobic conditions, thermophilic biodecomposition of organic matter at 40 to 60 percent moisture content produced fairly stable humus components during the decomposition process [37].

3.7 Yeast Treatment of distillery wastewater

Yeast, *Citeromyces* is the most studied organism for purifying municipality waste water, with great and consistent removal capacities in both colour and organic material. Under aerated and non-aerated circumstances, Yeast efficiently lowered the Chemical oxygen demand of synthetic wastewater by 95 % and 46 %, respectively, within one day [38].

3.8 Bacterial treatment of distillery wastewater

Melanoidin colour removal by microbiological straining is a relatively novel technique. The bacteria are capable of decomposing diverse xenobiotic complexes including melanoidin due to their versatility in the mechanism of nutrient intake. Ohmomo et al. (1988) investigated Melanoidin Decolorizing Activity in a number of facultative anaerobes (MDA) [39].

3.9 Fungal treatment of distillery wastewater

Fungus has outstanding adsorption properties due to its distinctive morphology (i.e. developed hyphae/mycelium). Fungi have a highly developed enzyme system that breaks down complicated compounds to produce metabolic energy. Fungi have been widely used for the disintegration and colour removal of melanoidin effluent due to their unique characteristics. Using the fungal *Coriolus sp.*, Watanabe et al. (1982) obtained substantial Melanoidin Decolorizing Activity (MDA). Melanoidin 0.5 percent solution was found to have a 77 percent reduction in darkness after 14 days at 30°C [40].

3.10 Membrane Treatment

This method is batch process termed as Emulsion liquid membrane (ELM) technique for treating spent wash. This method is very effective to removal of the color of Melanoidin waste water, limitations of this method are, membrane does not keep on intact while operating and unrestrained ionic strength, fouling of membrane, clogging of membrane, scaling and cleaning of membrane [41].

3.11 Electrocoagulation

Electrocoagulation process can be defined as generating metal ions by electro-chemical method (like Fe and Al) they destabilizes and neutralizes the electric charge of contaminants. Opposite charged pollutants stick each other to create a mass. This method has been shown to be quite successful in removing pollutants from water and it is distinguished by little sludge generation, the absence of chemicals, and convenience of use [42]. The different possible treatment methods of DSW and their results were shown in the table 2.

Table 2: Different treatment methods and their results

Sl no	Treatment	COD Removal (%)	Color Removal (%)	Reference
1	Adsorption Chitosan, a biopolymer was used as anion exchanger	99	98	Sekar et al., (1998) [43]
2	Phytoremediation	64	96	Billore <i>et al.</i> (2001) [35] Patel et al., (2001) [44]
3	Activated sludge process	93	Unsatisfactory	Torrijos et al., (1997) [36]
4	Yeast Treatment of distillery wastewater.	95	60	Malandra <i>et al.</i> (2003) [38] Raghukumar et al. (2001) [45]
5	Bacterial treatment of distillery wastewater	41	36.5	Kumar et al. (1997) [16]
6	Fungal treatment of distillery wastewater	51	70	Ohmomo et al (1987) [46]
7	Membrane Treatment	97.1	100	Nataraj et al. (2006) [47]
8	Electrocoagulation	85.7	96.09	Manoj et al., (2015) [09]

4 TECHNOLOGY

In 1889, the electrochemical technique of treating wastewater was first established in the United Kingdom [48]. Elmore patented mineral refinement by electrolysis in 1904. In 1909, the United States patented EC using aluminium and iron electrodes [49]. In early twentieth century, EC water purification process did not have much popularity. Due to developments in the treatment of industrial wastes, it has been popular in United States and Europe during the last decade. In North America, EC has mainly been used to industrial effluents from the pulp and paper, mining, and mineral industrial manufacturing [50].

In addition, EC has used to treating municipal waste water, removal of fluoride and phosphorous, leachate treatment, ammonia and phosphorus removal, textile waste water treatment, pre-treatment of pistachio processing industry wastewaters, foodstuff waste water, waste water containing oil, dyes waste water, effluents with high suspended particles, chemical and mechanical treatment of waste water, synthetic detergent waste water, mine waste water and heavy metal waste water. As of now, various empirical researchers are made on general classes of manufacturing wastewaters or waste flows, electro coagulation is

used to bring different operational parameter limits. The method is designed to utilise less electricity and produce more wastewater at all flow rates.

4.1 Electrocoagulation and Electrocoagulation mechanism

By applying an electric voltages to the type of media, various metal ions (such as Al and Zn) are generated, which destabilise, neutralise charges and thus separate contaminants in a liquid state, this process is known as electrocoagulation. Oppositely charged particles stick together to create a mass. This approach has been shown to be quite effective at separating pollutants from water, and it is distinguished by low sludge generation, the absence of chemicals, and convenience of use [42]. This electrochemical mechanism in water explained by Lin et al. (1998) is quite difficult. It is normally noticed that there are three probable mechanisms, viz., electro-coagulation (EC), electro-flotation (EF) and electro-oxidation (EO) [51]. Cat-ions of metals and metal hydroxide participate in the electrocoagulation process. Gas bubbles will remove pollutants by Buoyancy force to the liquid surface this process is termed as electroflotation. Hydrogen and oxygen bubbles generated will carry pollutants to the surface this process termed as electrolysis. Electro oxidation process involves breakdown of organic compounds by oxidation into carbon dioxide and water with other oxides compounds.

Can et al., (2003), Mullah et al., (2004) and Aji et al., (2012) explains EC process; metal ions generates from anodes electro-dissolution by Electrode reaction, and H₂ gas produced at the cathode thus disintegration of the particles, breaking suspension and disintegrating emulsions, destabilized particles aggregates forming mass, coagulated particles will settles by sedimentation action or removal of pollutants by electro-flotation by produced H₂ gas bubbles generated at cathode from water reduction reaction, bringing the solids to the surface of the liquid. Organic particle reduction occurs due to produced metal ion by chemical and electro chemical reactions [52-54].

The procedure of electrocoagulation is carried out in a precision (correct form and size) volume reactor containing one pair of electrodes such as anode and cathode. The anode substance is oxidized/corroded electrochemical redox processes when the reactor is powered by an external power source. Sacrificial electrode materials are used to describe the electrically conducting plates. The sacrificial anodes and cathodes are formed in same or different substances, and the sludges in liquid form is kept uniform in the container by using a mechanical or magnetic stirrer.

In electrolysis reaction, anodic reactions take place at positive side and cathodic reactions take place on negative side. Iron, aluminium, copper, zinc like consumable metals are generally used as sacrificial anodes to constant production of ions in the water. Charges of the particles neutralized by producing ions and hence it will implementing coagulation. The produced ions eliminate objectionable pollutants either by chemical reaction and precipitation or by causing the colloidal particles to coalesce which will separate by flotation process. Due to electric field created by applied EMF will moves contaminants, colloidal particles and oils. Physical and chemical characters of water and contaminants will be changed due to Ion formation, hydrolysis action, electrolysis action and free-radical formation. As a result of these complex pollutant particles converted to soluble compounds [55], pH, contaminant type and concentration, bubble size and location, floc formation and stability and agglomerate size all influences the operation of the EC unit.

4.2 Advantages and Dis-advantages of EC

Advantages: The contaminant can be carried to the top of the solution by the gas bubbles formed during electrolysis, where it can be collected. When compared to other separation procedures, there is less sludge produced, and the formed sludge settles quickly. Due to the presence of metallic oxides/hydroxides, dewatering is quite simple. Simple to use, little upkeep, and simple to operate. Because there is no external addition of chemicals to the system, there is no secondary pollution. It can handle practically every form of wastewater with issues including colour, odour, COD, TDS, and so on. It has the capability of settling tiny colloid particles.

Dis-advantages: Passivation of electrodes is caused by the growth of an oxide layer on the electrode surface. If we maintain a gelatinous mixture for a long time without separating it, it may dissolve. Electrodes must be maintained and replaced on a regular basis.

5. CONCLUSIONS

On a big scale, anaerobic, aerobic, physico-chemical and biological approaches for decolorization and removal of COD from distillery effluent have been developed, but no method has yet proven to be effective on large scale. By recovering methane gas, anaerobic treatment of distillery waste wash was effective. There is potential to apply a variety of advanced techniques. Use a procedure that can treat spent wash without diluting it and with a shorter hydraulic retention period. Electro-coagulation combined with aeration can be used to treat post-methanated distillery effluent. The rate of oxidation will be accelerated due to the aeration, and effective decolorization will be achievable. Electro-coagulation is more effective at treating spent wash, but it creates secondary sludge in the process. Because ozone is a potent oxidising reagent, a clean procedure and takes less time, this constraint can be solved by utilising a combination of ozone treatment and electro-coagulation. The structure and properties of the dark brown color causing reagent melanoidin are currently unknown.

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